

Consortium

The consortium consists of 13 partners from ten (10) European countries: Greece, Luxembourg, Belgium, Ireland, Switzerland, Germany, France, Portugal, United Kingdom and Malta.

Project Coordinator: Dr George Bravos
Institution: INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY FOR MARKET LEADERSHIP (ITML)
Email: gebravos@itml.gr
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Duration: 36 months
Participating organisations: 13
Number of countries: 10

SENTINEL

 @SentinelH2020

 company/sentinel-eu-project/

 sentinelh2020@gmail.com

www.sentinel-project.eu/

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SENTINEL

Bridging the security, privacy and data protection gap for smaller enterprises in Europe

SENTINEL at a glance

SENTINEL will bridge the security and personal data protection gap for European SMEs/MEs, by raising awareness and boosting their capabilities in the domain through innovation at a cost-effective level.

This vision will be realised by integrating tried-and-tested security and privacy technologies into a unified digital architecture and then applying disruptive Intelligence for Compliance.

Combined with a well-researched methodology for application and knowledge sharing and a wide-reaching plan for experimentation for innovation, SENTINEL will help small enterprises feel considerably more secure and safeguard their and their customers' assets.

OBJECTIVES

Develop and support a flexible, efficient and secure end-to-end digital Privacy and Personal Data Protection (PDP) compliance framework and Identity Management System (IdMS) for SMEs/MEs

Provide technological advances in automated data protection compliance assessment, such as tailor-made automated requirements engineering as a service, Machine Learning anomaly detection & recommendation systems and a Unified IdMS

Provide novel tools and services for enabling highly automated PDP compliance in SMEs/MEs

Validate, demonstrate and carry out experimental evaluation of the proposed framework on real-world SMEs/MEs operation scenarios

Raise awareness, collaborate with standardisation bodies and ensure technology transfer of project's results via EU digital innovation hubs

Boost the effectiveness of the EU data economy by offering high Technology Readiness Level solutions (TRL6-7)

USE CASES

ClinGenics - A microenterprise

Implementing extra security measures for accessing genomic sequence and personal data from a bioinformatics platform-software pipeline.

Tristone Investment Group - An SME

Homogenising the approach to data protection and compliance across multiple portfolio businesses through a single platform

UNINOVA - SMEs/MEs engaged via Digital Innovation Hubs

Assessment of compliance regarding privacy and personal data protection within an ecosystem of SMEs and MEs

